

CHARACTERIZATION OF IMPACT INDUCED DAMAGE MODES IN SINGLE LAP JOINTS OF WOVEN GFRP COMPOSITES

R. S. Choudhry^a, S. Li^a, R. Day^b

^aSchool of MACE, The University of Manchester

^bNWCC (North West Composites Centre), The University of Manchester

Sackville Street, M60 1QD, Manchester, UK

r.choudhry@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Single lap joints of woven GFRP composites have been investigated for impact induced damage modes using C-scan, X-ray micro tomography, imaging and finite element (FE) modelling. This has allowed for damage modes to be observed in 3D from macro to micro level – resulting in much better understanding of damage mechanisms and realistic FE modelling.

Keywords: Impact Damage, Single Lap Joints, X-ray Micro Tomography, Ultrasonic C-scan, Composite Failure theories.

INTRODUCTION

When a structure made from fibre reinforced polymeric composites is subjected to impact loading, the resulting damage is often quite complex in terms of both multiplicity and unpredictability of damage modes. If the structure involves bonded joints the complexity is increased further. Since the use of composite materials is continuously increasing in all type of structural components the impact threat can no longer be dealt with simplified design approaches and unrealistic in-service operating requirements. Important examples from the aerospace industry of the use of composite joints include bonded step lap joints used in attachments for the F-14 and F-15 horizontal stabilizers as well as the F-18 wing root fitting, and a majority of the airframe components of the Lear Fan and the Beech Starship [1]. The poor understanding of impact induced damage mechanisms necessitate the use of generous safety factors for product design. This often results in offsetting the weight saving advantage promised by composite materials, which is a consequence of their higher in-plane specific modulus and strength. Hence, from both an academic and industrial point of view it is important to increase the understanding of impact damage in bonded joints of composites.

Single lap joints which are the focus of this study are inherently less suitable for many types of loading due to their tendency of lateral deflection (or out of plane bending) that results in increased peel stresses as compared with their double lap counterparts [1]. Practical considerations such as geometry requirements and manufacturing

limitations, however, can often mean that they are the only design choice [2]. In recent years, due to the increasing use of adhesive bonding in the composites industry and less available information in literature regarding the behaviour and design of these joints, many authors have analyzed composite bonded joints from various perspectives. For instance Herszberg *et al.* [3, 4] have undertaken FE analysis and proposed a structural health monitoring system for composite ship joints (T – joints) and other marine structures. Li *et al.* [5,6] have used Mode I and Mixed Mode “cohesive zone” models to study adhesive joints failure. Ashcroft *et al* [7] have used electronic speckle pattern shearing interferometry (ESPSI) and x-radiography to experimentally observe tensile fatigue damage in adhesively layer. Wahab *et al.* [8] has developed an FE model to predict fatigue life of adhesively bonded multidirectional composites. The model only considers adhesive failure as the dominant damage mechanism. Gómez *et al.* [9] have developed a Bond-Graph model for hybrid adhesive/mechanical joints of composites. Potter *et al.* [10] have studied the effect of using various paste adhesives with unidirectional carbon/epoxy adherends in a double lap joint configuration under fatigue loading. In another recent study Kim [11] has specifically looked at damage formation mechanisms in single lap joints having composite adherends under impact loading. His study looks at the damage mechanisms using ultrasonic C-scan only and the finite element model is limited to pre-failure analysis. Other recent studies of adhesively bonded lap joints include work by Quaresimin and Ricotta [2, 12], Odi and Friend [13] and Kim [14]. A unique aspect of Kim’s numerical work is this that in addition to bond failure he has also considered adherend failure. Only one failure mechanism for adherend failure under tension i.e. delamination is considered in his work, however, and that only to the point of initiation using an empirical quadratic failure criteria. To validate his model he has only observed damage in two dimensions using high resolution digital photographs of the samples.

The brief review given above is representative of the various approaches that have been adopted for addressing damage in bonded composites in recent years. It highlights that firstly only a few authors have specifically looked at impact induced damage. Secondly even when impact response is studied; it is not with a view to characterize and establish the damage modes arising due to such loading. Thirdly most of the studies have not attempted to take a holistic view of the problem (that is considering both adherend and adhesive failure and taking in account both macro and micro failure mechanisms). In fact most of these studies consider a relatively weak adhesive with stronger adherends that limit the crack propagation to be in either entirely the adhesive layer or at best the adhesive adherend interface. The current study goes beyond this and tries to observe the impact induced damage modes in three dimensions and in its entirety i.e. both adherend and bond failure, taking stock of both macro and micro failure mechanisms. The view that has been taken in this study is this that the problem of damage mode characterization in bonded joints of composites should not be viewed in isolation of the problem of damage mode characterization in laminated composites; in fact it will become clear in this paper that in many ways it is a subset of the same problem with added geometric and material constraints that dictate the overall damage modes. This paper only focuses on the experimental observations of damage mechanisms while the numerical modelling and other experimental aspects of the work are detailed elsewhere [15-17].

METHODOLOGY

A systematic and comprehensive experimental and numerical investigation was carried out to understand the impact damage response of composite joints. The methodology followed is explained using figure 1.

Figure 1: Methodology

The lap joints for this study were made using Primco-SL246/40, which is a glass fibre/phenolic pre-preg. (8 harness satin weave glass fabric pre-impregnated with modified phenolic resin mix to a nominal 40% resin content). The joints were co-cured using Quick Step with a 0/0 (anti-symmetric) layup (no additional adhesive used; the resin in pre-preg acts as the adhesive) with four laminas in each adherend. The overlap widths that were tested are 21, 25, 36 and 46 mm. Impact tests were carried out in low velocity and low energy range (energy range 1.5 J – 8 J, velocity range 4 ms^{-1} – 10 ms^{-1}). Surface pressure measurement were taken by using a very thin pressure measuring film (Pressurex®) pasted on the front face (the face to be impacted) of the overlap. Specimen preparation was done using Quickstep™ plant at Northwest Composites Centre (NWCC), The University of Manchester. The details of the Quickstep™ process can be found in reference [18, 19]. Quickstep is a recent innovative manufacturing method for composites. It was developed to overcome three major operational difficulties with autoclaves, i.e. high costs compared to other processing methods, slow production rates and high pressure requirements (hence stringent safety regulations). Quickstep while addressing these three issues produces parts with quality comparable (and in some cases better) than autoclaves.

DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION TECHNIQUES

Three main techniques have been used to identify damage, create damage thresholds and characterise damage modes. These are

1. High resolution through transmission photographic imaging using back lit samples (to allow through transmission of light)
2. Ultrasonic C- Scan

3. 3D X-ray micro-tomography

Optical microscopy was also used, however, to a very limited extent. The use of these three different techniques allowed the author to study the damage at various levels.

The first technique of illuminating the sample with a high intensity light from the backside and then imaging, is often used with glass fibre reinforced composites, due to the semi-transparent nature of these composites. If used properly (by adjusting light and image contrast/balance etc) comparable level of qualitative information can be obtained using this technique for glass fibre composites as obtained with a through thickness C-scan. This technique has been used in some previous studies (for example [20, 21]). The comparison of pre and post impact images reveals the extent of damage with damage zones appearing darker. As an example of the images obtained using this technique, Figure 3 shows a 25 mm overlap width specimen, which was impacted with 4.5 J (6.68 ms^{-1}) of energy at 5 mm away from the centre of the overlap. In this image the indentation zone and the delaminated zone can be differentiated, however this information alone is not sufficient for detailed damage mode study.

C-scan is a popular ultrasonic testing method and in metals related industry its use is a routine practice. For composite manufacturers however, the scans are not always straight forward to interpret. This is because of the presence of various interfaces within the material. Taking a consistent and reliable reading is not always easy, due to diffraction and refraction effects, peak frequency downshift and non-linear propagation in water [22]. C-Scan is most commonly used as a 2D technique. C-Scan system used for this study is a 2-axis computer controlled water jet inspection system from Midas NDT. The system was used in through transmission mode with unfocussed, 10 MHz probes. Figure 4 shows a C-scanned image of the sample whose backlit image was shown in figure 3. The delamination zone is more pronounced in this image and the alternating dark and light fringes indicate that crack opening for delaminated zone is not uniform across the width of the specimen and there may be zones which have not yet completely delaminated.

Figure 2 A 21 mm overlap width specimen – impact energy 4.5 J: Note the major delamination/disbond failure due to load being off-centre

Figure 3 C-scan showing a 21 mm overlap width specimen – impact energy 4.5 J

This study has made extensive use of x-ray micro tomography (XMT) for more detailed macro and micro level damage observation. XMT is one of the computed tomography (CT) techniques and refers to reconstructing a volume from its cross sectional projections. The cross sectional projections are obtained from x-ray transmission [23] data. Since different materials absorb x-rays to different extent the internal micro-structure of an object can be revealed using the contrast difference. XMT works particularly well if the levels of attenuation offered by the constituents are significantly different. This was one motivation for choosing glass/phenolic composite for this study as carbon/epoxy composites offer lesser contrast and hence are difficult to examine using this technique. XMT allows for observing damage at any location within a material. Virtual cross sectional images or 3D surface views can be generated at any depth and at any required angle without any need for cutting. Using multi-planar views one can simultaneously generate cross-sectional images in different planes for any point or region of interest. This capability is not available with microscopy (optical or SEM). With microscopy at best only a small number of sections in a one particular plain can be observed. The process of obtaining these sections is also physically intrusive and inevitably leads to additional damage hence compromising the true picture of damage within a material. XMT to a large extent overcome all these limitations.

The tomography system (HMXST 225) was supplied by X-Tek systems Ltd. AEA Technology's software Tomohawk Version 4 was used for data acquisition and CT reconstruction. Control of the X-ray source was with X-Tek Systems' iXS software. The software used for generating 3D surface models, creating video animations and other image processing tasks was Amira version 3.1.1 and version 4.0.

In the following paragraph a few examples of views generated using XTM will be shown and the damage modes highlighted. It is important to note that these are only representative slices and in actual hundreds of virtual slices for each sample are generated. Based on those images the damage modes and mechanisms are identified. As a first example figure 4 shows three orthogonal slices through the overlap region of a 21 mm overlap joint impacted with 4.5 J (6.68 ms^{-1}) energy. Figure 5 shows a slice through the specimen a section where the both delaminations can be seen. While the C-scan and through transmission photographs only indicate an overall damaged area, here we can exactly see the location, extent and connectivity of delaminations. Two more examples of XTM images are shown in figures 6 and 7. These images are for a 25 mm sample impacted with 8 J (9.6 ms^{-1}) of energy. The images show two different damage modes, which have been named as fibre tow splitting and fibre push out, in two different laminas of the same specimen. The image in figure 6 is lower

section of lamina 4 while that in figure 7 is lower surface of lamina 8. For each specimen XTM was done at various resolutions hence revealing damage features ranging from millimetre to micro meter range.

Figure 4 Note the micro indentation damage zone and the two delaminations (approximate diameter of scanned region is 20 mm)

Figure 5 Section view showing the delaminations A and B

Figure 6 Tomography slice showing extensive fibre two splitting

Figure 7 Tomography slice lamina 8 – of the specimen in previous figure, note how the weave has been spaced out – This mechanism is being called fibre push out.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The damage mechanisms observed for single lap co-cured joints of woven glass fibre reinforced composites due to impact loading are strongly influenced by, the impactor energy, impactor velocity, overlap width and the impact location (relative to both overlap width and boundaries). Besides these the boundary condition, and the shape and rigidity of impactor are also expected to be important factors in determining the impact damage response but these were taken as constants in the current study. Based on the particular combination of these parameters the joint under impact may fail through bond failure, adherend failure or a combination of both. Table 1 summarises the relationship of damage modes with impact energy and overlap widths.

The observed failure mechanisms can be categorised as

1. Micro damage modes

a. Micro indentation

This is the indentation that takes place directly under and around the impact location for a hemispherical impactor. The indentation is due to the plastic deformation of matrix under combined compressive and shear loading. This is generally not visible on visual inspection but can be picked up by C-scan and XMT.

b. Fibre tow splitting or loosening

Fibre tows in the region of micro indentation become flattened and loosen slightly. Loosening here means that the spacing between fibres in the tow has increased and become inconsistent. This appears to be because of the matrix deformation that is arrested by the underlying fibre tows. This phenomenon was picked up by XMT.

c. Micro matrix cracks – at fibre matrix interface

Small interface cracks start to appear in the matrix in and around the indentation zone. These are present in almost all lamina interfaces to varying degrees. The cracks are too small to be called delamination and

are normally localized in the interstices location of the crimping weave pattern.

d. Localized fibre tow rupture

If the impact energy is sufficiently high then the loosened fibre tows may also break at some points, this does not normally mean a rupture of a whole tow, instead it usually involves rupture of loosened fibres within the tow.

2. Delaminations

For co-cured, centrally impacted, single lap joints, both experiments and simulations show maximum delamination damage at bond interface and varying degree of delamination damage at other interfaces. The delamination damage may be classified based on initiation and propagation mechanism and the location (bond interface or adherend interfaces) at which it takes place. These are,

- a. Disbond – can take place in two ways independent of each other or in combination depending on the joint width.
 - i. Delamination initiating from back side joint free edge and propagating across the bond interface without deflection. This is mainly due to type I loading. More commonly observed for narrower overlap joints.
 - ii. Propagate outwards from directly under impactor from the indentation zone under shear loadings, mostly gets arrested by collapsing weave. This is mostly under mixed mode with type II component being more significant. More common for wider overlap joints.
- b. Adherend delaminations – may also take place in two ways independent of each other or in combination depending on the joint width and impact location.
 - i. for centrally impacted specimens depending on joint width delamination in adherends may initiate between any lamina interface under mixed mode conditions and normally grows outward from the indentation zone. In this case there may be significant failure mode interaction which usually results in the arrest of delamination front and other failure mechanisms becoming more significant.
 - ii. for off-centric loading delaminations in adherend may also initiate from joint free edges under type I loading.

3. Macro Damage Modes

These are generally not observed for small overlap width specimen which at higher energies fail by complete bond failure. For those specimens which have sufficient overlap area to prevent type 1 dominated complete bond failure, the following mechanisms are usually observed.

a. Macro indentation and bulge

If the matrix has significant ability to yield under shear (as in current study) then for higher energy cases micro indentation turns into macro indentation and bulging.

b. Matrix cracks

In-plane and out of plane matrix cracks develop in the indentation zone. These generally result in complete loss of support to fibres.

c. Fibre push out

The fibres in the indentation zone are pushed out of the matrix. Further increase of impact energy will usually lead to catastrophic failure of fibre tows.

Table 1. Damage mechanisms for single lap joints having composite adherends under impact loading.

	Damage	1.64J / 4.02ms ⁻¹	3.01J / 5.51ms ⁻¹	4.53J / 6.68ms ⁻¹	6.2J / 7.86ms ⁻¹	8.01J / 9.6ms ⁻¹	Higher
20 mm	Surface VID	None	None	Some	Less	Very less	
	Micro indent	Some	Significant	Significant	Significant	Some	
	Delamination	None	Joint Free edge	Significant if load off centric	Very Significant	Dominant	
	Macro indent	None	None	Some	None	None	
	MMC ¹	None	None	None	None	None	
	FWF ²	None	None	None	None	None	
25 mm	Surface VID	None	None	Some	Some	Significant	Dominant
	Micro indent	Some	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant
	Delamination	None	Joint Free edge	Joint Free edge	Significant if load off centric	Significant	Significant
	Macro indent	None	None	Some	Some	Significant	Dominant
	MMC ¹	None	None	None	None	Some	Significant
	FWF ²	None	None	None	None	Some	Significant
35 mm	Surface VID	None	Some	More	Significant	Dominant	
	Micro indent	None	Some	Significant	Significant	Significant	
	Delamination	None	None	None	None	None	
	Macro indent	None	None	Some	Significant	Dominant	
	MMC ¹	None	None	None	None	Some	
	FWF ²	None	None	None	None	Some	
45 mm	Surface VID	None	Some	More	Significant	Dominant	Dominant
	Micro indent	None	Some	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant
	Delamination	None	None	None	None	None	Significant
	Macro indent	None	None	Some	Significant	Dominant	Dominant
	MMC ¹	None	None	None	None	Some	Significant
	FWF ²	None	None	None	None	Some	Some

1. MMC = Macro Matrix Cracking ; 2. FWF = Fibre Weave Failure ; Indent = Indentation

The damage propagation and energy absorption mechanisms for co-cured joints, having woven fibre-reinforced composite adherends, vary considerably with overlap width. In the low velocity/energy regime there exists a lower characteristic overlap width such that if the overlap width is less than the characteristic width the dominant failure mode is always a combination of micro damage under the impactor nose and a delamination/disbond that initiates from back side joint free edge and propagates across the bond interface, primarily due to bending moment resulting in peel type loading of joint. Similarly for the same energy and velocity range an upper characteristic width can also be defined such that if the overlap width is greater than

that; the dominant failure is always a combination of micro damage modes and macro damage modes, with no macro delamination and disbond. Interfacial matrix cracks, however, do exist in the indentation zone but these do not appear to propagate in a continuous manner and hence are not being referred to as delamination. For the energy and velocity range investigated in this study the lower characteristic width was qualitatively found to be around 20 mm while the upper characteristic width was found to be around 35 mm. This characteristic width is specific to a particular joint geometry and boundary condition.

A greater reduction in shear strength after impact was observed as compared with tensile strength after impact. Based on strength reduction data and damage area data obtained in this study it is noted that for single lap joints it is dangerous to rely on a damage tolerance threshold established using only the percentage damage area measure from C-scan. This is because the use of C-scan based percentage damage area threshold for damage tolerance is valid only if joint width is around the lower characteristic width (i.e. the dominant failure mode is delamination) but if it is above this than the range may or may not be valid as in this case the mechanisms characterized as macro damage mechanisms become significant and these may result in significant strength reduction (especially shear strength) without an appreciable change in overall damaged area as observed using C-scan.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author gratefully acknowledges the financial support of National University of Sciences and Technology, Pakistan and The University of Manchester, UK

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